

Lignite and biomass waste hydrothermal liquefaction crudes upgrading by hydrotreatment.

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ABSTRACT

Hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) is a promising process for the energetic valorization of low-value feedstocks. However, HTL crude oils are incompatible with the existing fuel standards, making their upgrade imperative. Nonetheless, the hydrotreatment of HTL crude oils is still a challenge due to the complex nature of the feedstock. Therefore, this work explores the relationship between the HTL crude oil origin and the HDT conversion. Five HTL crude oils from different feedstocks, i.e., Oak Sawdust, Brewer's Spent Grain (Spent Grain), Sewage Sludge from two origins, and Lignite, and their detailed characterization by elemental analysis, ¹³C and ³¹P NRM, molecular weight distribution, comprehensive 2D-GC chromatography, and Simdis, were compared to that of the HDT liquid product. Lignite displayed the highest potential for producing hydrocarbons, particularly monoaromatics and naphthenes, among the feedstocks tested. The capacity of Lignite HTL crude oil to be transformed into hydrocarbons was associated with the absence of compounds resistant to HDT in this feedstock. Similarly, Oak sawdust also displayed a higher selectivity towards aromatic and naphthene hydrocarbons, due to the significant concentration of aromatic compounds in the crude oil. In opposition, the Sewage sludge and Spent Grain crude oils were particularly selective towards aliphatic

hydrocarbons, particularly paraffins, produced from aliphatic components, like amides, in the crude oil. However, these feedstocks were rich in nitrogenated aromatics, e.g., carbazole, which are recalcitrant to hydrotreatment and were not fully converted during the reaction.

The differences observed in the HDT liquid composition show that the HTL crude oil composition dictates the potential for producing hydrocarbon fuels. Indeed, HTL crude oils rich in aromatic compounds will yield preferentially naphthenes and aromatic hydrocarbons. In opposition, crude oils richer in aliphatic carbon will be more selective towards paraffins. The nature and concentration of heteroatom components must also be considered since these must be imperatively eliminated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Among thermochemical processes capable of upgrading waste and low-value materials, hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) is a technology that can accommodate a variety of wet and dry feedstocks into an energy-dense product¹. The potential of the HTL process has been demonstrated in the valorization of renewable waste feedstocks, like algae, sewage sludges, lignocellulosic wastes²⁻⁶, and non-renewable low-value matter, e.g., low-grade coal⁷⁻⁹. In this latter case, before combustion for electricity combustion, Lignite can be converted by HTL to increase HHV on one side and get an oil crude compatible for fuel production on the other side.

Independently of the feedstock, complex reactions and the combined pathways between each of the components in the feedstock, e.g., cellulose, lignin, proteins, ..., lead to a viscous crude oil, which contains a wide diversity of molecules from monomers and oligomers to condensed molecules. However, the heteroatom content, mostly O and N, must be eliminated to transform these crude oils into suitable fuels. Furthermore, the crude oils from HTL are composed of highly unsaturated molecules with high molecular weight, which must be upgraded, i.e., hydrogenated and cracked, to meet fuel standards.

The removal of heteroatom compounds from biocrude compounds proceeds through hydrotreatment and occurs by breaking the heteroatom-carbon bond with hydrogen. Hydrotreatment is a common

process in oil refineries, which allows for the reduction of S content to reach fuels specifications (hydrodesulfurization) and to reduce basicity from nitrogen compounds (hydrodenitrogenation) protecting acidic catalysts used in subsequent processes, e.g., cracking or hydrocracking¹⁰. Additionally, hydrodeoxygenation is used in biorefineries producing fuels from vegetable oils or oil refineries when coprocessing bio-oil and fossil fuels¹¹.

The conversion of these complex feedstocks into hydrocarbons compatible with the standard fuel pool is not trivial, and challenges, such as complete heteroatom removal and catalyst deactivation, are still the subject of intense research^{2,12}. Furthermore, the complexity and nature of the compounds to be upgraded change significantly with the feedstock, thus making it difficult to find a one-fits-all solution. Still, the PNNL (Pacific Northwest National Laboratory) was able to successfully upgrade HTL feedstocks from algae¹³, sewage sludges, and food waste^{13,14}, under pilot-scale hydrotreating units by using identical, yet harsh, reaction conditions, i.e., $T = 400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P_{\text{H}_2} = 100\text{ bar}$. An alternative approach is to upgrade the HTL crude oils in two stages. The first stage, performed under milder conditions ($T \approx 250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), aims to stabilize the crude oil, i.e., eliminate highly reactive compounds, e.g., aldehydes, sugars, etc., and the second stage focuses on eliminating heteroatoms^{15,16}. The effectiveness in the removal of heteroatoms, either via one-stage or two-stages hydrotreatment, will significantly depend on the used catalyst and, most importantly, on the nature of the compounds in the crude oil, which is tied to the HTL feedstock. Consequently, different crude oils will require different degrees of hydrotreatment severity to reach fuel specifications. Furthermore, the composition of the crude oil will dictate the overall fuel yield and the potential for the production of different types of fuel, e.g., gasoline and diesel¹⁷.

This article aims to explore in depth the reactivity of several types of feedstocks from renewable, i.e., Oak Sawdust, Brewers Spent Grain, Sewage Sludge from two different sources, and non-renewable, i.e., Lignite, origin to yield hydrocarbon fuels through sequential HTL and hydrotreatment, performed by using robust sulfide catalyst (NiMoS/P-Al₂O₃). The HTL crude oils and HDT reaction liquid product were deeply characterized via elemental analysis, gel permeation chromatography (GPC/RI and

GPC/DAD), ^{13}C and ^{31}P NMR, Simdis, and comprehensive 2D-GC chromatography (GC \times GC/FID, MS, and TOF) to provide a clear image of their composition. The detailed characterization of the reagent (HTL crude oil) and the HDT products was used to identify the main reaction pathways occurring during the hydrotreatment of each feedstock.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Crude oil production

Five crude oil samples were prepared by using five different feedstocks: Lignite from the coal mine of Bełchatów in Poland, provided by PGE Górnictwo i Energetyka Konwencjonalna SA; Sewage sludge from a municipal sewage treatment plant in Rybnik, Poland, stabilized by anaerobic fermentation and supplied by PWiK Rybnik (denoted Sewage S. 1); Pelletized sewage sludge from municipal sewage treatment plant in Bissingen, Germany, supplied by RWE (denoted Sewage S. 2); Brewer spent grains, provided by Freiberg Brewer in Germany; and, Oak sawdust provided by Kurtok Parkiety in Poland. The feedstocks' physicochemical properties are in Tables S1 to S5.

The HTL experiments were conducted in a batch-type 1000 ml stainless steel autoclave reactor (Autoclave Engineers, USA), equipped with a magnetically coupled mechanical stirrer. Each HTL experiment had 600 g of slurry containing 10 wt.% solid feedstock (on a dry basis) in water. After loading the reactor, the residual air was removed by nitrogen purging and vacuuming four times. Subsequently, the vessel was pressurized with N_2 (~2 bar) and then heated to 360 °C (reaction temperature) with a constant heating rate 10 °C/min and maintained at this temperature for 30 min (HTL reaction time). The final pressure in the reactor vessel was self-generated.

After completion of the reaction, the autoclave was cooled to ambient temperature, and the HTL products mixture (crude oil, aqueous phase, and char) were recovered from the reaction vessel. The solid and liquid products obtained after the HTL process were separated using a vacuum filtration

technique. First, the post-reaction mixture was filtered on glass microfiber filters and then the aqueous phase obtained was separated from the char. The reactor vessel and char were washed with acetone, and the solid and liquid organic fraction (crude oil) solution in acetone were separated by vacuum filtration. Next, the solid fraction was dried to constant weight in the laboratory drying oven at 105 °C. Finally, the filtered bio-oil solution was concentrated using a rotary vacuum evaporator. The scheme of the process is presented in Figure S1, and crude oil, gas, and char yields are shown in Table S6.

2.2. Hydrotreatment

The hydrotreatment of the crude oils was performed under batch conditions using a 300 mL reactor from Parr (Model 4566). The hydrothermal conversion of 3 g of crude oil was performed in the presence of 25 g of n-heptane (solvent) and 1 g of sulfided NiMo/Al₂O₃ catalyst (characterization in Table S7). n-Heptane was considered inert during the reaction and is used to provide enough volume inside the reactor to enable continuous stirring (\approx 700 rpm) and, consequently, facilitate the contact between HTL oil, hydrogen, and catalyst. Additionally, the relatively low boiling point of n-heptane (bp = 98.4°C at 1 atm) enabled the evaporation of the solvent with minimal loss of the liquid phase products. It should be mentioned that, under reaction conditions, n-heptane is in the supercritical state, which has been demonstrated to enhance the hydrotreatment by facilitating the supply of H₂ to the catalyst¹⁸⁻²⁰. Before the reaction, the catalyst was activated through sulfidation carried at 400 °C for 3 h, under a continuous flow (4 L/h) of H₂S (15%) in H₂. The activation procedure was performed ex-situ in a quartz U-tube reactor. After sulfidation, the catalyst is kept under an inert atmosphere (N₂) until being transferred into the reactor. After flushing with H₂ at room temperature, the reactor was pressurized with 10 bar of H₂ to prevent severe coke formation on the catalyst during heating and then heated up to 375 °C (reaction temperature). Once the reaction temperature was attained, an additional pressure of 50 bar of H₂ was introduced into the reactor, reaching a total pressure of 100

bar. After the second H₂ introduction in the reactor, the crude oil hydrotreatment was performed for 5 h leading to a pseudo-contact time of 0.6 h⁻¹.

$$\text{Pseudo contact time (h}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{m_{oil}}{m_{cat}t_{reaction}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where: m_{oil} and m_{cat} are the mass of crude oil and catalyst, respectively, and $t_{reaction}$ is the reaction time).

After the reaction, the reactor was cooled to room temperature, and the residual gas was collected in a gas bag and analyzed in a micro-GC (SRA instruments). The liquid and spent catalyst were separated through filtration, and the heptane in the liquid was evaporated, in a rotovap, for 2 h at a pressure of 30 mbar and temperature of 40°C. The liquid remaining after evaporation was considered the liquid product from hydrotreatment. The soluble products in the spent catalyst were extracted through Soxhlet, using heptane as the solvent. The yield of gas (Equation 1), liquid (Equation 2), and solid (Equation 3) were determined according to the following equations:

$$\text{Yield}_{gas} \text{ (wt. \%)} = \frac{\sum \frac{y_i P_{cold} M_{w_i}}{(V_{reactor} - V_{heptane}) R T_{ambient}}}{m_{crude\ oil}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$\text{Yield}_{liquid} \text{ (wt. \%)} = \frac{m_{liquid}}{m_{crude\ oil}} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

$$\text{Yield}_{solid} \text{ (wt. \%)} = \frac{m_{spent\ cat} - m_{cat}}{m_{crude\ oil}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where: y_i is the compound i gas composition; P_{cold} is the total pressure of the reactor when cold, M_{w_i} is the molecular weight of the compound i ; $V_{reactor}$ is the volume of the reactor (300 mL); $V_{heptane}$ is the volume of heptane; R is the molar gas constant; $T_{ambient}$ is the temperature of the reactor after cooling; $m_{crude\ oil}$ is the mass of crude oil; m_{liquid} is the mass of liquid after heptane evaporation; $m_{spent\ cat}$ is the mass of used catalyst after Soxhlet extraction; and, m_{cat} is the mass of fresh sulfided catalyst used in the reaction.

2.3. Characterization methods

Elemental compositions (CHNS-O) of the crude oils and hydrotreatment liquid products were analyzed on a Thermo Scientific FLASH 2000 Organic Elemental Analyzer (accuracy of ± 0.1 wt.%). Additionally, the sulfur composition of the crude oil and the sulfur and nitrogen composition of the hydrotreated liquid samples were also quantified using an ANTEK 9000NS apparatus (detection limit level = 1 ppm). The samples were diluted on THF (≈ 5 wt.%) before analysis on the ANTEK 9000NS apparatus.

The elemental composition of crude oil and the hydrotreatment liquid were used to determine the hydrotreatment extent of deoxygenation (Equation 5), desulfurization (Equation 6), and denitrogenation (Equation 7).

$$\text{Deoxygenation (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{O_{\text{HDT liquid}}}{O_{\text{crude oil}}}\right) \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

$$\text{Desulfurization (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{S_{\text{HDT liquid}}}{S_{\text{crude oil}}}\right) \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$$\text{Denitrogenation (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{N_{\text{HDT liquid}}}{N_{\text{crude oil}}}\right) \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

The ^{13}C -NMR analysis of the HDT liquid and crude oil samples was performed in a Bruker AVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer and analyzed using TopSpin 3.0. The measurements were performed at room temperature with an accumulation of 4700 scans for approximately 15 h. The HDT liquid fraction and crude oil (100 mg) were diluted in 0.6 mL of deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3) and DMSO (DMSO-D_6), respectively. Table S8 includes the chemical shifts attributed to each functional group.

The quantification of the hydroxyl groups in the lignite crude oil was performed by quantitative ^{31}P liquid NMR performed in a Bruker AVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer. Prior to analysis, the crude oil (≈ 30 mg) was dissolved in 0.3 mL of solution A ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{pyridine} = 1 : 1.6$ vol/vol), mixed with 0.2 mL of N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), 0.1 mL of solution A containing 22.0 mg/mL of cyclohexanol (internal standard), and 0.1 mL of solution A containing 5 mg/mL of chromium (III) acetylacetonate (relaxation agent). Afterward, 0.1 mL of 2-chloro-4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaphospholane (CTMDP) was added to the crude oil solution and vortex for a few minutes. The final solution was then analyzed by ^{31}P liquid NMR. The chemical shift ranges used for the attribution of the hydroxyl group functional groups are shown in Table S2.

The molecular weight distribution of the compounds in the lignite crude oil and the hydrotreatment liquid was obtained by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) using an Agilent 1200 series HPLC equipped with two PLgel Columns (50 and 500 Å), a refractive index detector (RID), and a diode array detector (DAD). The analysis was carried out at 35 °C using tetrahydrofuran (THF – 1 mL/min) as eluent.

Before analysis, the samples were diluted to a concentration of ≈ 1 wt.% in THF and filtered (0.45 μm). A mixture composed of linear hydrocarbons with a molecular weight (Mw) comprised between 86 to 1000 g/mol (extrapolated above) was used as the standard to convert elution time into molecular weight (hydrocarbon equivalent).

The boiling point distributions of the hydrotreatment liquid products were determined utilizing simulated distillation (Simdis – ASTM 2887) by using an Agilent 7890 gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a 10 m \times 0.53 mm \times 0.88 μm ZB-1XT capillary column. The hydrotreatment liquid product was separated into fuel-relevant fractions according to their typical boiling point range (bp), i.e., naphtha (bp < up to 175 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), kerosene (bp = 175 -250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), middle distillates (bp = 250 – 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), and heavy fraction (bp > 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The relationship between boiling point and retention time was established using a mixture of linear paraffin with carbon-number between 6 (bp = 69 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and 44 (bp = 545 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The detected products quantification was made using a standard diesel sample as a reference (initial bp = 114 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and Final bp = 475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Comprehensive GC \times GC-MS, GC \times GC-TOFMS, and GC \times GC-FID were used to identify and quantify the compounds in the crude oils and HDT liquid. The GC \times GC-MS and GC \times GC-TOFMS systems were equipped with a cryogenic modulator from Zoex Corporation (USA), as described in ref ²¹. The chromatography and TOFMS parameters are described in Tables S9 and S10. The GC \times GC/FID was equipped with a switch valve modulator (Agilent G3486A CFT modulator), and modulation parameters were optimized according to ref ²². The parameters used for the analysis are described in Table S10. The compounds detected by GC \times GC/FID were quantified using the relative responsive factor method (RRF)²³ with cyclohexanol as the reference.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Hydrothermal liquefaction crude oil characterization

Five crude oils obtained from the hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of Lignite, Oak Sawdust, Brewer spent grain, and two samples of sewage sludge, from a municipal sewage treatment plant Rybnik, Poland (Sewage S. 1) and a municipal sewage treatment plant in Bissingen, Germany (Sewage S. 2), were used as feedstocks for hydrotreatment. The elemental composition of the HTL crude is presented in Table 1, and the van Krevelen diagram is shown in Figure 1. All samples showed a significant presence of heteroatom compounds, i.e., O, S, and N, demonstrating the need for the hydrotreatment

stage to produce liquid fuels. According to Figure 1., the two sewage sludge samples, particularly Sewage S. 2, have the highest H/C ratios ($H/C = 1.43-1.52$), indicating they should contain a smaller concentration of aromatic compounds than the remaining. Significant concentrations of oxygen, sulfur, particularly in Lignite and Sewage sludge samples, and nitrogen in sewage sludge and Spent grain were also observed (Table 1 and Figure 1). The elemental composition of the HTL crude oil reflects the feedstock used in the HTL process. Indeed, sewage sludge samples typically contain higher concentrations of proteins and lipids than the remaining feedstocks⁵, which justifies the significant N concentrations and the higher H/C ratio. Indeed, the composition of the sewage sludge feedstocks used to produce the oils (Tables S4 and S5) shows an N concentration of 5.4 wt.% and 6.0 wt.%, respectively, in Sewage S. 1 and Sewage S. 2. Similarly, these feedstocks also contain relatively high concentrations of S, i.e., 0.4 wt.% and 1.3 wt.%, respectively for Sewage S. 1 and 2, which justify the relatively high concentration of this element in Sewage S. 1 and Sewage S. 2. Similarly, the Lignite feedstock contains 2.4 wt.% of organic sulfur that can be transferred to the crude oil fraction during HTL. Like sewage sludge, Spent Brewer grain includes a high concentration of proteins (19-30 wt.%)^{24,25}, justifying the high N content of the feedstock (4.7 wt.% - Table S8) and HTL oil (4.3 wt.% - Table 1). Unlike the remaining feedstocks, Oak Sawdust's lignocellulosic nature is well known to contain low sulfur and nitrogen content (Table S9), which was reflected in the low concentration of these elements on the crude oil (Table 1).

Figure 1. 3D-plot of the molar ratio between H/C, O/C, and N/C of the HTL crude oils used in this work. Blue, green, and orange dots represent the 2D plots of O/C vs. H/C, O/C vs. N/C, and N/C vs. H/C, respectively.

The concentration of hydroxyl groups (OH) from phenol, aliphatic alcohols, and carboxylic acids in the crude oils is shown in Table 1. The contribution of the OH groups to the crude oil's overall oxygen composition changed significantly depending on the feedstock, with the following trend being observed: Oak Sawdust (55.9 %) > Lignite (38.4 %) > Sewage S. 2 (28.0 %) > Sewage S. 1 (23.0 %) > Spent Grain (15.9 %). Independently of the crude oil, phenols were the main OH contributors (Table 1). In the particular case of oak sawdust and Lignite, phenols represented 48.4 % and 34.8 % of the crude oils oxygen, respectively, which agrees with the high aromatic ^{13}C -O occurrence observed for these samples in ^{13}C NMR (Figure 2). The high occurrence of phenol compounds in oak sawdust and lignite crude oils is directly linked to the feedstock chemical structure. For example, during HTL the

lignin component of lignocellulosic biomass primarily yields phenols ^{2,26}. Similarly, Lignite also contains a significant amount of oxygenated aromatic compounds ²⁷, which are converted to phenols during HTL. On the other hand, the oxygen in cellulose, hemicellulose, lipids, and proteins is preferentially converted into acids and aliphatic alcohols, which are highly soluble in water, ketones, amides, esters, lactones, and among others ²⁸. Hence, justifying the lower concentration of OH groups in the sewage sludge and spent grain samples, which are particularly rich in lipids and proteins. The second largest contribution to the OH groups is provided by the carboxylic acids, which represent between 2.4 % (Lignite) and 9.8 % (Sewage S.2) of the crude oils' oxygen content. Finally, aliphatic alcohols represent 1.0 % (Spent Grain) to 4.3 % (Sewage S.2) of oxygen in the samples.

The heating values (HHV) of the crude oils are shown in Table 1. Despite the changes in the composition of the crude oil samples, minor variations were observed in the calorific values (HHV – Table 1), i.e., between 36.3 and 30.5 MJ/kg. The small variation in the HHV of the oils is linked to their similar composition in H and C, which are the main contributors to the calorific value according to the formula proposed by Channiwala et al. ²⁹. Furthermore, the overall range of the HHV of the crude oils is compatible with the typical values found in the literature for similar feedstocks and process conditions, i.e., HHV \approx 30-36 MJ/kg^{2,4}.

Table 1. Elemental composition of Hydrothermal liquefaction crude oils.

	Lignite	Sewage S. 1	Sewage S. 2	Oak Sawdust	Spent Grain
C (wt.%)	74.1 ± 1.0	76.0 ± 0.1	70.3 ± 1.4	71.7 ± 0.2	66.0 ± 2.0
H (wt.%)	7.8 ± 0.1	9.1 ± 0.1	8.9 ± 0.2	7.3 ± 0.8	7.5 ± 0.2
S (ppm)	17,060	13,047	8,505	914	519
N (wt.%)	< 0.1	4.6 ± 0.1	5.3 ± 0.1	< 0.1	4.3 ± 0.1
O (wt.%)	13.1 ± 0.8	8.9 ± 0.1	8.2 ± 0.7	18.6 ± 0.7	12.1 ± 0.1
HHV ^a (MJ/kg)	33.7	36.3	34.1	31.7	30.5
Hydroxyl group characterization (%- O basis) ^b					
Aliphatic OH	1.2	3.3	4.3	1.2	1.0
Phenolic OH	34.8	14.9	13.9	48.4	8.6
Acid OH	2.4	4.8	9.8	6.3	6.4
Total	38.4	23.0	28.0	55.9	15.9

^a The high heating value (HHV) were determined by using the expression from ²⁹.

^bpercentage of oxygen as hydroxyl (OH) group.

Figure 2. Crude oil carbon functional group composition determined by ^{13}C NMR. NMR spectra in Figure S2 and chemical shift attribution in Table S1.

The functional group composition of the HTL crude oils determined by ^{13}C NMR can be seen in Figure 2. For all samples, aliphatic C-H and aromatic carbon, represented by C-O, C-C, and C-H bounds, are the most abundant contributions to the composition of the crude oils. However, the relative proportions between aromatic and aliphatic carbon are highly dependent on the nature of the feedstocks used to produce the HTL crude oil. For instance, for Lignite and Oak Sawdust, a higher aromatic content was observed, with the $\frac{\text{Aromatic Total}}{\text{Aliphatic C-H}}$ ratio being 1.24 and 1.36, respectively. In opposition, Sewage S. 1 and Sewage S. 2, and Spent Grain displayed higher concentrations of aliphatic carbon, as observed by the $\frac{\text{Aromatic Total}}{\text{Aliphatic C-H}}$ ratios of 0.71, 0.55, and 0.76, respectively. Indeed, the

$\frac{\text{Aromatic Total}}{\text{Aliphatic C-H}}$ ratios of the samples agree with their overall composition in carbon and hydrogen

(Figure 1), which already indicated a higher concentration of aromatics in the Lignite and Oak Sawdust crude oils. In addition, these samples also contained higher C-O bounds, including aromatic and aliphatic C-O, aldehydes, ketones, acids, esters, and methoxy functional groups (Figure 2), which is in agreement with the higher O concentration determined by elemental analysis (Table 1).

The concentration of aromatic C-C bounds in crude oils is representative of molecules with two or more conjugated aromatic rings, i.e., polyaromatics. While the overall concentration of aromatic compounds in crude oils changed significantly, minor variations were observed in the C-C bound concentration among samples (Figure 2). Only Sewage sludge samples, particularly Sewage S.2 (6.4 %), displayed a slightly smaller concentration of C-C bounds indicating these samples should contain less polyaromatic compounds.

Figure 3. A) Molecular weight distribution ($Mw_{Hydrocarbon}$) of the crude oil samples determined by refraction index (RI). B) Absorption at $\lambda = 290$ nm as function of the compounds molecular weight distribution ($Mw_{hydrocarbon}$).

The hydrocarbon molecular weight equivalent ($Mw_{Hydrocarbon}$) distribution of the HTL crude oils, analyzed by RID, is displayed in Figure 3-A, revealing a wide distribution of products. Except for Oak

sawdust, all crude oils contained molecules with a $Mw_{\text{Hydrocarbon}}$ inferior to 1,500 g/mol with max intensity between 200 g/mol and 300 g/mol. On the opposite, Oak Sawdust contained compounds with a $Mw_{\text{Hydrocarbon}}$ up to 2,000g/mol due to the presence of a secondary lump centered at $\approx 1,200$ g/mol, which can be attributed to the transformation of the lignin component of lignocellulosic biomass under HTL conditions as proposed by Castellví-Barnés et al.³⁰. Hence, the crude oil obtained from Oak Sawdust displayed the highest average $Mw_{\text{Hydrocarbon}}$ of the studied crude oils, i.e., 357 g/mol, followed by Sewage S. 2, Sewage S. 1, Spent grain, and Lignite, in which average $Mw_{\text{Hydrocarbon}}$ was 301 g/mol, 281 g/mol, 272 g/mol, and 271 g/mol.

SEC-DAD provides the samples' UV absorbance and gives information on aromaticity. Figure S3 (SEC-DAD of HTL crude oils) and Figure S7 (SEC-DAD of upgraded HTL oils) illustrate the evolution of aromatic contributions and can be compared to reference compounds in Fig S9-S11. The UV absorption at $\lambda=290$ nm, corresponding to polyaromatic compounds, was selected for drawing Figure 3-B. The crude oil obtained from Oak Sawdust exhibited the most intense absorption, with a second peak at 1200 g/mol clearly indicating heavier polyaromatic compounds. Similar observations were made by Jarvis et al. when comparing the composition of crude oils from sewage sludge to those from pine wood measured by FT-ICRMS³. The authors clearly show a much higher concentration and distribution of polyaromatic compounds in the lignocellulosic samples than in sewage sludge, which was richer in aliphatic species. Much like Oak Sawdust, the crude oil from Spent grain also displayed high UV absorption indicating a significant concentration of polyaromatic compounds, even though this contains significantly less aromatic carbon than oak sawdust or Lignite (Figure 2). Indeed, the analysis and quantification of spent grain composition by comprehensive GC×GC/TOF-MS (Figure S4) and GC×GC/FID (Table 2), respectively, clearly shows this sample abundance in polyaromatic hydrocarbons, indoles, and carbazoles, particularly when compared with Lignite.

Despite the high aromatic carbon fraction determined by ¹³C NMR (Figure 2), Lignite crude oil UV absorption was significantly less intense than the Oak Sawdust and Spent Grain crude oils (Figure 3-

B), suggesting the concentration of polyaromatic compounds in this sample to be smaller. Hence, the high concentration of Lignite aromatic can be attributed to a significant presence of monoaromatic hydrocarbons or non-conjugated polyaromatic hydrocarbons, e.g., biphenyl, which display a similar UV absorption pattern than monoaromatics, e.g., benzene. Additionally, the high C-C bond concentration found in ^{13}C NMR for the lignite crude oil (8.9% of ^{13}C) can also be explained by a higher alkylation degree of the aromatic compounds.

The composition of the crude oils was determined by comprehensive GC×GC-TOFMS (Figure S4) and quantified by GC×GC/FID (Table 2), respectively. As expected, the composition of the crude oils depended highly on the type of feedstock used for its production. Sewage S.1 and Sewage S. 2 contained very similar chemical composition, which was dominated by the presence of nitrogenated compounds, including amides, indoles, carbazoles, pyridine, pyrazine, and a wide variety of aromatic compounds with N and O. Similar product compositions of heavy compounds were observed by Jarvis et al. and Hiraclous et al. when analyzing sewage sludge HTL crude oils via FT-ICR/MS^{3,15}. The significant presence of aromatic-N and aromatic-N+O compounds in HTL crudes is characteristic of the Maillard reaction between amino acids and carbohydrates of the feedstock, which are known to condense and produce highly reactive amines and ammonia, also responsible for the transformation of fatty acids into the observed fatty amides²⁸. Despite the different origins, the two sewage sludge samples showed a close composition, with the main difference being a higher occurrence of aromatic-N, like indoles and amides in Sewage S. 2. Still, it should be mentioned that only 22.0 wt.% and 30.7 wt. of Sewage S. 1 and Sewage S. 2 were quantified by comprehensive GC×GC/FID, which leaves a significant portion of the samples unaccounted. Indeed, the Mw distribution of the crude oils (Figure 3-A) showed the presence of molecules up to 1,500 g/mol, while the detection limit of comprehensive GC×GC/FID analysis is < 600g/mol (boiling point \approx 520°C).

Much like sewage sludge, the crude oil from spent grain feedstock contained a significant amount of nitrogenated compounds, including amides, indoles, carbazole, pyrrole, and aromatic compounds

containing N and O (Figure S4 and Table 1). Furthermore, this feedstock yielded a significant amount of polyaromatic hydrocarbons, thus justifying the intense UV absorption observed in Figure 3-B. The formation of polyaromatic hydrocarbons under hydrothermal conditions can occur through multiple mechanisms, including Diels-Alder addition and hydrogen abstraction acetylene addition (HACA) mechanism, with phenols, proteins, and monoaromatic HC being considered common precursors³¹. Thus, the coexistence of lignocellulose, which yields phenols and ketones, and protein in the spent grain feedstock, could help explain the higher concentration of polyaromatic hydrocarbons in this sample. Similarly, the lignocellulosic structure of oak sawdust can also explain the presence of phenols, ketones, and furans, as shown by Yang et al.³² and Barnés et al.³⁰. The crude oil produced from this feedstock represents the main fraction (18.4 wt.%) detected by comprehensive GCxGC/FID. While most oak sawdust's crude oil compounds detected through comprehensive GCxGC analysis are monoaromatic, it should be mentioned that only 20 wt.% (Table 2) of the sample was accounted for through this technique. Indeed, according to FT-ICRMS analysis of crude oils from pine wood performed by Jarvis et al. and Sudasinghe et al. most aromatic compounds in the samples contain one or more oxygen groups [3,30], which significantly increases the boiling point of the molecules and the retention in the GC column. Furthermore, Figure 3-B shows Oak sawdust crude oil polyaromatics to have a heavier Mw than those from Spent Grain.

The chemical composition of the compounds detected through comprehensive GCxGC of Lignite's crude oil was very similar to that of Oak Sawdust (Table 2), i.e., high concentration of ketones and phenols (18.0 wt.%). Despite the high sulfur concentration of this crude oil, i.e., ≈ 1.7 wt.%, only trace amounts of thiophene were observed. The qualitative analysis of the sulfur compounds through the Simdis method using an FPD⁺ detector (Figure S5) clearly shows sulfur to be present only on compounds heavier than the detection limit of GCxGC-TOFMS, i.e., retention time $> C_{36}$, thus explaining the absence of those compounds in the detected molecules.

Table 2. Chemical composition of the HTL crude oils determined by comprehensive GCxGC/FID (compound families identified by comprehensive GCxGC/TOF). The comprehensive GCxGC/TOF 2D-chromatograms are displayed in the supplementary information Figure S4.

Families of compounds	Lignite (wt.%)	Sewage S. 1 (wt.%)	Sewage S. 2 (wt.%)	Oak Sawdust (wt.%)	Spent grain (wt.%)
Paraffins and Naphthenes HC ^a	1.2	4.3	0.5	0.7	2.5
MonoAromatics HC ^a	1.3	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.8
Polyaromatics HC ^a	1.0	-	-	-	4.0
Phenols and other oxygenated molecules	18.0	2.0	1.5	18.4	7.1
Indoles + Aromatic-N	-	4.4	10.0	-	4.0
Amides and aliphatic – N	-	8.7	15.3	-	15.1
Other (oxy- / Nitro- genated)	-	2.4	2.1	-	2.9
% detected	21.5	22.0	30.7	20.0	36.5

^a HC: Hydrocarbon

3.2. Hydrotreatment of HTL crude oils

While the composition of the crude oils highly reflected the nature of the feedstock used in the HTL process, their composition is incompatible with that of liquid fuels. Thus, a hydrotreatment stage is required to remove heteroatoms, i.e., S, O, and N, and hydrogenate the aromatic hydrocarbons into more appropriate saturated hydrocarbons. Hydroconversion also enables to convert heavy molecules into lighter ones. Table 3 shows the product distribution obtained after the hydrotreatment of the crude oils. Three different fractions, i.e., liquid, solid, and gas, are directly measured, while the amount of H₂O is estimated through an oxygen balance to the reaction system. The product quantification after the reaction (mass balance) corresponded to 76 wt.% - 92 wt.% of the overall feedstock introduced into the reactor. The missing mass was attributed to loss during heptane (solvent) evaporation, performed at 40 °C and 30 mbar for 2 h, which removed light compounds with boiling points between C₅ (36 °C) and C₈ - C₉ (bp = 125 - 151°C).

The hydrotreatment of Lignite's crude oil led to the lowest solid yield, i.e., 2.8 wt.%, while the remaining crude oils' solid yield stayed between 6.7 wt.% and 8.7 wt.%. It should be mentioned that no solid material, e.g., char, was observed after the reaction. Consequently, the solid product

corresponds to matter deposited on the catalysts, e.g., coke or minerals. Zho et al. studied the impact of coprocessing HTL crude oil from sewage sludge with diesel during hydrotreatment, observing increased carbon content on the spent catalyst and the presence of K, Ca, and Fe on the catalyst³⁴. The semi-quantitative analysis of the inorganic elements in the crude oil is shown in Table S12, showing the presence of Si, Fe, and other trace elements, such as Ca, Zn, and P, in all crude oils. Therefore, it is not surprising that significant amounts of Fe (0.2 to 1.0 wt.%) and Si (0.2 to 0.7 wt.%) were observed on all spent catalysts (Table S13). It is worth mentioning that inorganic ash in HTL crude oils as been reported to promote the polymerization of reactive compounds, like acids and aldehydes, leading to the formation of solids³⁵. Furthermore, the deposition of coke and minerals on the catalyst can significantly affect the catalyst's performance, leading to premature deactivation³⁶. Consequently, the lower solid yield obtained with the crude oil from Lignite would suggest this feedstock promotes less deactivation of the NiMoS/P-Al₂O₃ catalyst.

Table 3. Product fractions yield for the hydrotreatment of the crude oils.

	Lignite	Sewage S. 1	Sewage S. 2	Oak Sawdust	Spent Grain
Liquid (wt.%)	58.8	63.8	63.8	41.6	55.5
Gas (wt.%)	15.3	8.1	4.4	8.7	16.8
Solid (wt.%)	2.8	8.7	6.7	8.4	7.9
O as H ₂ O (wt.%) ^a	11.8	7.8	8.0	17.4	11.6
Total (wt.%)	88.7	88.6	82.9	76.1	91.8

^aH₂O amount estimated through oxygen mass balance ($O_{H_2O} = O_{Lignite\ oil} - O_{HDT\ liquid} - O_{gas}$)

The yield of gas products, i.e., CO, CO₂, and light hydrocarbons up to C₄, highly depended on HTL crude oil nature (Tables 3 and 4). Under hydrotreatment conditions, methane formation can be associated with the conversion of methoxy groups^{37,38}, and methanation of CO and CO₂^{39,40}. Similarly, light hydrocarbons, such as ethane and propane, can be formed from HDO, HDN, and HDS of small molecules, which can be produced during the conversion of the larger molecules existing in the crude. Finally, CO and CO₂ are produced from decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions.

Except for Spent Grain's crude oil, methane was the main component in the gas, followed by light hydrocarbons, CO, and small amounts of CO₂ (Table 4). On the other hand, spent grain's crude oil displayed a higher selectivity towards light hydrocarbons and methane, with no CO and minimal CO₂ (0.1 wt.%) observed (Table 4). As mentioned previously, methane is primarily produced from the conversion of methoxy groups and the methanation of CO and CO₂. According to the ¹³C NMR of the crude oils (Figure 2), Oak Sawdust crude oil contains the highest methoxy, acid, ester, ketone, and aldehyde carbon content. Yet, hydrotreatment of Lignite crude oil produced the highest methane yield, i.e., 9.2 wt.% vs. 5.9 wt.% in Lignite and Oak Sawdust crude oil, respectively, suggesting another source for the methane product in Lignite. For instance, Lignite crude oil contains a significant amount of sulfur (1.7 wt.%), which is removed during the hydrotreatment process (Table 5). Thus, the excess of methane and light hydrocarbons observed during the hydrotreatment of Lignite can be a by-product of the fragmentation of larger molecules during HDS. Indeed, in coal, sulfur is commonly present in side chains as alkylthio groups^{41,42}, which during HDS yield light hydrocarbons. It should be mentioned that the carbon in α position to S atoms displays an NMR shift in the range attributed to the aliphatic C-H (0 – 55.2 ppm)⁴³. A similar phenomenon can explain the high C₂-C₄ alkane yield observed during the hydrotreatment of the Spent Grain crude oil. The presence of sugars and proteins in the feedstock promotes the formation of Maillard reaction products, such as pyrazine and derivatives, which during HDN yield light gases, like ethane and propane.

Table 4. Product fractions yield for the hydrotreatment of the crude oils.

	Lignite	Sewage S. 1	Sewage S. 2	Oak Sawdust	Spent Grain
CO	1.9	1.4	1.0	1.1	-
CO ₂	0.2	-	-	0.3	0.1
CH ₄	9.2	4.5	2.0	5.9	3.4
C ₂ -C ₄	4.0	2.3	1.4	1.4	13.4
Total (wt.%)	15.3	8.1	4.4	8.7	16.8

Much like for solid and gas, the nature of the crude oil also impacted the yield of liquid product (Table 3), with the sewage sludge samples, i.e., Sewage S. 1 and 2, displaying the highest liquid production

(Yield_{Liquid} = 63.8 wt.%), followed by Lignite (Yield_{Liquid} = 58.8 wt.%), spent grain (Yield_{Liquid} = 55.5 wt.%) and Oak Sawdust (Yield_{Liquid} = 41.6 wt.%). The elemental composition of the liquid products is shown in Table 5. As expected, the concentration of C and H significantly increased compared to the crude oil samples. At the same time, the amount of heteroatom compounds, i.e., S, N, and O, was reduced due to the hydrotreatment reactions promoted by the NiMoS/P-Al₂O₃ catalyst. The higher H/C ratio on the liquid samples (Table 5) indicates less aromatic compounds than the respective crude oils (Figure 1), as these are hydrogenated to naphthenes during the hydrotreatment or partially hydrogenated for polyaromatics. Yet, the H/C ratio of the liquid depended on the parent crude oil nature, with the Oak Sawdust liquid product displaying the lowest H/C observed among the liquid products (1.40), followed by Lignite (1.60), Sewage S. 2 (1.71), Spent Grain (1.77), and Sewage S. 1 (1.79). While the amount of H/C of the departing crude oil is an important factor dictating the amount of hydrogen contained in liquid product, the nature of the compounds in the crude oil is crucial to determine the H/C evolution during hydrotreatment. For instance, the H/C of the Oak Sawdust and Lignite crude oils and hydrotreatment liquid was, respectively, 1.22 and 1.26, and 1.40 and 1.60, indicating the compounds in Lignite crude oil hydrogenate more easily. Such a phenomenon can be explained by the much higher concentration of polyaromatic compounds and phenols in Oak Sawdust crude oil (Table 1 and Figure 3), which are challenging to convert to naphthenes and paraffins⁴⁴. It should be mentioned that the maximum H/C ratio is 2 for naphthenes and ≈ 2.1 for alkanes. Therefore, the concentration of aliphatic carbon in the liquid products, particularly those obtained for the Sewage Sludge and Spent grain samples, is expected to be high, as demonstrated by the ¹³C NMR results (Figure 4).

Regarding heteroatom removal, in all cases, the concentration of O in the liquid products was below 1.0 wt.%, with the oxygen concentration being below the detection limit on the liquid obtained from the lignite crude oil. It should be mentioned that a small number of compounds in the ¹³C NMR shift attributed to aromatic C-O bonds were observed (Figure 4). Yet, no oxygenated compounds were

detected during comprehensive GCxGC/MS analysis (Figure S8), suggesting any trace of O to belong to the small fraction of high Mw compounds not observed through this technique.

Nitrogen removal is particularly challenging in biobased feedstocks, as compounds like carbazoles are particularly recalcitrant to hydrotreatment^{45,46}. Still, for the liquid products obtained from high N content crude oils, i.e., Sewage S. 1 and 2, and Spent Grain denitrogenation was between 88-91%. The relatively high denitrogenation rate can be attributed to the significant concentration of N in the form of amides and amines, which are more easily transformed than aromatic-N compounds⁴⁷, and to the good performance of NiMoS/P-Al₂O₃ catalysts to promote HDN reactions⁴⁵. Still, after hydrotreatment, the nitrogen concentration, mainly in the form of nitrogenated aromatic compounds like indoles and carbazoles (Figure S8), in the liquid product was between 0.4-0.6 wt.% on Sewage S. 1, Sewage S.2, and Spent Grain. While no specification states a maximum N concentration in hydrocarbon fossil fuels and HTL-derived fuels are not regulated yet, synthetic aviation fuels (SAF) have a limit of 2 ppm⁴⁸. Furthermore, nitrogenated compounds impact other regulated properties, such as gum content, storage stability, and thermal stability⁴⁹. Consequently, further reducing the N content in the hydrotreatment liquid products obtained from the sewage sludge and spent grain, either by performing a second hydrotreatment or blending with cleaner fuel, would be preferable before usage. Similarly, the sulfur concentration in all liquid products is above the 10 ppm specification, thus further desulfurization should be required. Nonetheless, no sulfur-containing compound was observed through GCxGC/MS analysis of the hydrotreated liquid products, suggesting S to be present on the heavier compounds of the liquid and not on the fuel-relevant fraction of the liquid, i.e., compounds with boiling point below 350°C.

Table 5. Elemental composition of liquid product obtained from the hydrotreatment of the HTL crude oils.

	Lignite	Sewage S. 1	Sewage S. 2	Oak Sawdust	Spent Grain
C (wt.%)	90.5 ± 1.4	86.8 ± 1.3	84.2 ± 0.1	89.9 ± 1.7	84.9 ± 0.3
H (wt.%)	12.1 ± 0.3	13.0 ± 0.1	12.0 ± 0.2	10.5 ± 0.3	12.5 ± 0.1
S (ppm)	75	114	15	38	192
N (ppm)	32	4147	5716	Below detection	5089
O (wt.%)	Below detection	0.3 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1
H/C (mol/mol)	1.60	1.79	1.71	1.40	1.77
HHV (MJ/kg) ^a	45.9	45.6	43.4	43.7	46.0
Deoxygenation (%)	> 99	96.6	89.0	94.6	93.3
Desulfurization (%)	99.6	99.1	99.8	95.8	63
Denitrogenation (%)	< 97	91	89	≈100	88

^a The high heating value (HHV) were determined by using the expression from ²⁹.

The functional group compositions, obtained through ¹³C NMR, of the hydrotreatment liquid products are shown in Figure 4. As expected, the concentration of aliphatic C-H bonds significantly increases compared to the parent crude oils due to the hydrogenation capacity of the NiMoS/P-Al₂O₃ catalyst. A reduction of the aromatic, particularly aromatic C-O, methoxy CH₃-O, aldehyde, ketone, acid, and ester bonds was observed for all samples. Of all crude oils, the one produced from Oak sawdust was where the concentration of aromatic carbon saw the smallest reduction in the HDT liquid product, i.e., 44.3 % in the HDT liquid when compared to 49.3% in the HTL crude oil. The lower aromatic hydrogenation rate observed on the oak sawdust sample could be attributed to the large molecular weight and polyaromatic nature of the components in the Oak Sawdust crude oil (Figure 3). Indeed, while the crude oil from Lignite displayed a similar aromatic carbon content to Oak Sawdust, i.e., 49.6 % vs. 49.3 %, respectively, the Lignite's HDT liquid product only contained 27.1% of aromatic compounds, suggesting the difference in aromatic conversion is related to the nature of the compounds. It is worth mentioning that, according to ¹³C NMR (Figure 2) and the van Krevelen diagram (Figure 1), Lignite and Oak contained the highest concentration of aromatic compounds. Consequently, unsurprisingly, the liquid products from these samples display a higher concentration of aromatic carbon.

Figure 4. Hydrotreated liquid product carbon functional group composition determined by ^{13}C NMR. NMR spectra in Figure S6 and chemical shift attribution in Table S8.

The molecular weight distribution of HDT liquid products is shown in Figure 5-A. Unlike the HTL crude oil, no products with more than 1,000 g/mol were observed, indicating a significant molecular weight reduction due to the HDT reaction, particularly through the removal of the high molecular weight compounds. Indeed, the average Mw of the HDT liquid products stayed between 126 g/mol and 203 g/mol, while the crude oils Mw remained between 271 g/mol and 357 g/mol. Among the different feedstocks, Oak sawdust showed the highest variation in average Mw, i.e., from 357 g/mol to 126 g/mol, with Oak Sawdust's HDT liquid displaying the lowest Mw of the tested feedstocks. Furthermore, the Oak Sawdust's liquid product Mw distribution does not display a second lump as observed on the parent crude oil (Figure 3-A). The disappearance of the second lump and the significant Mw reduction observed during Oak Sawdust crude oil HDT can be attributed to the substantial presence of $\text{C}_{\text{aromatic}}\text{-O-C}_{\text{aromatic}}$ ether bonds of lignin fragments in the crude, under HDT conditions, which are broken, yielding significantly smaller molecules. N. Sudasinghe et al. also observed the oxygenated aromatic compounds in pine wood HTL crude oil, mainly from lignin, under significant conversion during HDT

conditions³³. The low Mw of the compounds in the Oak Sawdust liquid product can justify the lower liquid yield (41.6 wt.%) and poorer mass balance (76.1 wt.%) obtained with this sample compared to the remaining feedstocks, as the lower molecular weight and, consequently, boiling point (bp < 150 °C) compounds, were removed during heptane evaporation procedure.

Much like Oak Sawdust, Lignite HDT liquid average molecular weight (142 g/mol) was significantly smaller than that of the parent crude oil (271 g/mol). However, the lignite nature is different from that of Oak Sawdust. Still, the high yield of gas products (Table 4) from Lignite hydrotreatment suggests significant fragmentation from smaller groups, e.g., alkoxy (R-O) and alkylthio (R-S), existent in crude oil. Furthermore, the production of light gases from high Mw molecules can also justify the higher liquid yield (58.8 wt.%) and mass recovery (88.7 wt.%) observed during lignite crude oil HDT, as this mechanism is less likely to yield compounds removed during the solvent evaporation stage. Finally, Spent Grain, Sewage S.1, Sewage S.2 HDT liquid products displayed an average molecular weight of 187 g/mol, 203 g/mol, and 219 g/mol. The average molecular weight difference between crude oil and HDT liquid for Sewage S.1, Sewage S.2, and Spent Grain was ≈ 80 g/mol, suggesting a smaller contribution of molecular fragmentation to the HDT liquid.

Figure 5. A) Molecular weight distribution ($Mw_{\text{Hydrocarbon}}$) of the hydrotreated liquid products determined by refraction index (RI). B) UV absorption at $\lambda = 290$ nm as a function of the molecular weight ($Mw_{\text{Hydrocarbon}}$).

As expected, the UV absorption intensity in Figure 5-B was significantly smaller than that of the parent crude oils (Figure 3-B) due to the hydrogenation of the polyaromatic compounds during HDT. Except for Lignite, the UV absorption molecular weight range was equivalent to the refraction index's. However, in the case of Lignite, only compounds with a molecular weight below 500 g/mol displayed UV absorption at $\lambda = 290$ nm. In comparison, the overall molecular weight distribution showed the presence of compounds up to 750 g/mol. Therefore, in lignite HDT liquid, the compounds with conjugated aromatic rings are present only on the lighter fraction of the liquid.

Like the crude oils samples, Oak Sawdust displayed the most intense UV absorption, suggesting this sample contains the highest polyaromatics concentration of all liquids. In opposition, Lignite displayed the lowest UV absorption despite ^{13}C NMR results showing this sample to have the second largest concentration of aromatic carbon, with an aromatic C-C bond concentration equivalent to that of Oak Sawdust, i.e., 7.7 % vs. 13.6 %, respectively of aromatic C-C bonds in Lignite and Oak Sawdust HDT liquid. Thus, most of the aromatics in Lignite HDT liquid are monoaromatic with a high degree of alkylation. Indeed, GC \times GC/MS and GC \times GC/FID analysis (Figure S8) and quantification (Table 6) of Lignite and Oak Sawdust HDT liquid show a significantly higher concentration of polyaromatic compounds in the latter. Furthermore, the monoaromatic compounds in Lignite showed a high degree of alkylation and included naphthene rings in their composition (Figure S8), indicating these compounds result from the hydrogenation of polyaromatic compounds. As the rate of hydrogenation decreases as a function of the number of conjugated aromatic rings hydrogenated in polyaromatic compounds⁴⁴, the high concentration of aromatic carbon (Figure 4) observed in lignite HDT liquid can be explained by the polyaromatic hydrocarbons' lower capacity to undergo complete hydrogenation.

The liquid products obtained from the HDT of Sewage S. 1, Sewage S. 2, and Spent Grain crude oils all displayed similar UV absorption intensity as a function of molecular weight distribution (Figure 5-B). Even though Spent Grain HDT liquid displayed a similar UV absorption behavior to the Sewage sludge samples, the Spent Grain parent crude oils contained a significantly higher concentration of polyaromatics (Figure 3-B), suggesting the polyaromatic compounds in this feedstock to be more easily converted than the those of sewage sludge crude oil. Indeed, the comprehensive GCxGC analysis of the Sewage S. 1 and Sewage S. 2 crude oils (Table 2) demonstrated a much higher concentration of polyaromatic recalcitrant nitrogenated compounds, e.g., carbazoles, than that observed on spent Grain crude oil, which justifies the lower reduction in UV absorption observed on the Sewage sludge samples.

Table 6. Chemical composition of the liquid products obtained from the HDT of the HTL crude oils was determined by GCxGC/FID (compound families identified by GCxGC/MS). The chromatograms are displayed in the supplementary information Figure S8.

Families of compounds	Lignite (wt.%)	Sewage S. 1 (wt.%)	Sewage S. 2 (wt.%)	Oak Sawdust (wt.%)	Spent grain (wt.%)
Paraffins and Naphthenes	37.3	49.8	41.0	16.5	49.0
MonoAromatics	35.3	15.2	7.6	29.8	17.0
DiAromatics	11.5	-	0.3	14.7	5.5
Polyaromatics	2.6	-	-	6.9	2.5
Phenols and Aromatic - O	-	0.6	1.2	3.1	1.2
Aromatic - N	-	2.1	2.5	-	3.9
Aromatic O + N	-	6.7	8.6	-	-
% detected	86.7	74.4	68.2	70.9	69.0

The chemical composition of the HDT liquid products is shown in Table 6. Unlike crude oils, a significant amount, i.e., 86.7 wt.% – 68.2 wt.%, of the compounds in the sample were detected during comprehensive GCxGC/FID analysis. The increase in compound detection is directly linked to the lower molecular weight (Figure 5-A) and polarity of components in the HDT liquid. As suggested by the elemental analysis (Table 5) and ¹³C NMR composition, the liquid products display a significant

concentration of aliphatic hydrocarbon compounds (paraffins and naphthenes), with the higher concentration being observed on the Sewage sludge samples, particularly Sewage S.1 (49.8 wt.%), and Spent Grain (49.0 wt.%), followed by Lignite (37.3 wt.%). The high occurrence of aliphatic hydrocarbon compounds in the sewage sludge and spent grain samples can be explained by the presence of aliphatic nitrogenated compounds, such as aliphatic amides (Table 2), which are easily converted into paraffins under HDT conditions [44]. On the other hand, Lignite HDT liquid showed a high concentration of naphthenic compounds (Figure S8), suggesting that the hydrogenation of aromatics, including phenols and aromatic hydrocarbons significantly contributes to forming aliphatic compounds. Indeed, Lignite HDT contained the highest concentration of monoaromatic hydrocarbons (35.3 wt.%) of all samples, in addition to diaromatic (11.5 wt.%) and polyaromatic hydrocarbons (2.6 wt.%), which under HDT condition are hydrogenated to naphthenes. Similarly, Oak sawdust HDT liquid aliphatic hydrocarbon fraction contained a high proportion of naphthenes (Figure S8). Additionally, this sample was also rich in monoaromatic (29.8 wt.%), diaromatic (14.7 wt.%), and polyaromatic (6.9 wt.%) hydrocarbons originated from phenols, suggesting a similar conversion path to Lignite. It is worth mentioning that phenol conversion over sulphided catalysts, like NiMoS/P-Al₂O₃, are particularly selective towards aromatic hydrocarbons, with the aromatic ring hydrogenation pathway being less kinetically favored⁵⁰. Hence, justifying the high aromatic hydrocarbon concentration observed in Lignite and Oak Sawdust HDT liquids, which parent crude oils were particularly rich in phenols.

The presence of heteroatom-containing compounds was observed in all HDT liquid products except Lignite (Table 6). Indeed, as indicated by the low concentration of oxygen (O < 0.1 wt.% - Table 5), nitrogen (75 ppm), and sulfur (32 ppm), only hydrocarbon compounds were observed in the GC×GC-FID analyses of lignite HDT liquid. In opposition, small amounts of phenols were observed over Oak Sawdust (3.1 wt.%), Sewage Sludge S.1 (0.6 wt.%), Sewage S. 2 (1.2 wt.%), and Spent Grain (1.2 wt.%) can be attributed to hydrogen concentration of oxygenated compounds in the Oak Sawdust crude oil or the presence of the nitrogenated compound in the sewage sludge and spent grain crude oils (Tables 1 and 2), as these are known to inhibit HDO reactions^{51,52}. Finally, the presence of aromatic nitrogen-

containing compounds, i.e., indoles and carbazoles, was observed in the Sewage S.1 (2.1 wt.%), Sewage S.2 (2.5 wt.%), and Spent Grain (3.9 wt.%) samples. The significant concentration of aromatic nitrogenated compounds in the HDT liquid products from Sewage Sludge and Spent Grain HTL crude oils is related to the high concentration of nitrogen in the parent crude oils (Table 1) and the resistance of these compounds to HDN^{45,46}. Indeed, although aliphatic nitrogenated compounds, like amides, were the primary nitrogenated compounds observed in the HTL crude oils (Table 2), only aromatic compounds with nitrogen were observed in the HDT liquid.

Figure 6. Distillation curve of liquid products obtained from the HDT of the HTL crude oils determined by Simdis (ASTM 2887). Fuel boiling point ranges: Naphtha < 175°C; Kerosene = 175 – 250°C; Middle distillates = 250 – 350°C.

The distillation curves of the HDT liquid products are displayed in Figure 6. Lignite displayed the highest amount of products with a boiling point below 545°C (82.9 wt.% detection limit of ASTM 2887), followed by Spent Grain (81.7 wt.%), Oak Sawdust (74.0 wt.%), Sewage S. 1 (64.7 wt.%), and, finally, Sewage S. 2 (55.7 wt.%). Except for the Sewage sludge samples, the amount is matter detected

through the Simdis method (ASTM 2887) and comprehensive GC×GC/FID (Table 6) was quite similar, i.e., ± 4 wt.%. However, for Sewage S. 1 and Sewage S. 2, Simdis observed 10-13 wt.% less mass, despite the boiling point detection limit of both techniques being quite similar, i.e., $bp_{\text{limit}} = 545$ °C for Simdis and $bp_{\text{limit}} = 520$ °C for comprehensive GC×GC/FID. The significant difference between techniques samples can be attributed to using the effective carbon number method²³ of the Comprehensive GC×GC/FID results (Table 6). In opposition, the Simdis method assumes all compounds to be equal and have a response factor identical to hydrocarbons. However, nitrogen and oxygen in organic molecules negatively contribute to the FID response intensity²³. Hence, the high concentration of heteroatom-containing compounds in the sewage sludge HDT liquid artificially reduces the mass detected in Simdis.

The concentration of products in the naphtha range varied from 2.9 wt.% in the spent grain HDT liquid to 6.3 wt.% in Lignite (Figure 6). While the small amount of naphtha observed from all feedstocks can be attributed, in part, to the evaporation of heptane (solvent), multiple reports on the HDO of HTL crude oils under similar reaction conditions have reported similar results⁵³⁻⁵⁵. Consequently, more severe HDT conditions must be employed if necessary to increase naphtha range products, as demonstrated by P. Biller et al.⁵⁴.

The yield of kerosene range products (boiling point = 175 – 250 °C) highly depended on the feedstocks. Oak Sawdust and Lignite displayed the highest concentration of kerosene in the HDT liquid, respectively, with 24.5 wt.% and 20.7 wt.%, followed by the Spent grain and Sewage S. 1, each with 13.7 wt.%, and Sewage S. 2 (9.4 wt.%). Regarding the middle distillate fraction (boiling point = 250 – 350 °C), the highest concentration was found on the Spent Grain HDT liquid, which contained 38.6 wt.%, followed by Lignite (35.3 wt.%), Sewage S. 1 (28.1 wt.%), Oak Sawdust (25.4 wt.%), and Sewage S. 2 (24.0 wt.%). The boiling point distribution is a reflex of the HDT liquids' molecular weight distribution (Figure 5-A). For instance, the significantly higher concentration of kerosene products in the Oak Sawdust and Lignite HDT liquids agrees with the lower Mw of these samples (Figure 5-A).

Indeed, in a hydrocarbon mixture, such as the one used to calibrate the SEC-RI analysis, kerosene products would be comprised between a molecular weight of ≈ 128 g/mol (n-nonane – boiling point = 151 °C) and ≈ 198 g/mol (tetradecane – boiling point = 253 °C). On the other hand, Sewage S. 1, Sewage S. 2, and Spent grain distribution revealed a higher concentration of molecular weight compounds in the range of middle distillates, i.e., from ≈ 198 g/mol (tetradecane – boiling point 253 °C) to ≈ 296 g/mol (heneicosane – boiling point 356 °C), which is in agreement with the distillation profiles of these samples (Figure 6). It should be mentioned that the measures made by SEC-RI are not quantitative due to the variations in the refraction index (RI) of the molecules in sample. Thus, the observed discrepancies between the amounts calculated through Simdis (Figure 6) and the molecular weight distribution (Figure 5-A) are expected. Furthermore, the presence of heteroatoms in the organic molecules can lead to significant boiling point differences between molecules with similar molecular weights, e.g., carbazole (molecular weight = 167 g/mol, boiling point = 355 °C) compared to dodecane (molecular weight = 170 g/mol, boiling point = 216 °C). Indeed, despite being the liquid with a higher concentration of low molecular weight products (Figure 5-A), Oak Sawdust Simdis only detected 74 wt.% of the liquid, while Lignite and Spent Grain Simdis recovery was 82.9 wt.% and 81.7 wt.%, respectively.

The composition of the different fuel range products is presented in Figure 7. The composition of the naphtha was quite similar for all feedstocks (Figure 7), with aliphatic hydrocarbons representing the major compounds, i.e., 84 – 91 wt.%, and the remaining being represented by monoaromatic hydrocarbons. In opposition, the composition of the products in the range of kerosene displayed significant differences. Except for Lignite, all feedstocks contained heteroatom compounds in the kerosene range, mainly oxygenated aromatics like phenols, in a concentration ranging from 2.4 wt.% in Spent Grain to 8.2 wt.% in Sewage S. 2. A similar behavior was observed for the middle distillate fraction with the heteroatom fraction staying between 6.5 wt.% in Spent Grain and 16.6 wt.% in Sewage S. 2. On the other hand, Oak Sawdust kerosene and middle distillate were mainly composed of monoaromatic hydrocarbons, i.e., 55.4 wt.% and 53.3 wt.%, as opposed to the sewage sludge

samples, which contained 71 – 74 wt.% and 61 - 68 wt.% of aliphatic hydrocarbons. Finally, Lignite displayed an intermediate behavior with the kerosene fraction containing slightly more aliphatic hydrocarbons, i.e., 55.4 wt.% aliphatic hydrocarbons vs. 43.7 wt.% monoaromatic hydrocarbons, and the middle distillates products being mainly composed of aromatic hydrocarbons, including 49.5 wt.% of monoaromatic and 8.5 wt.% of diaromatic and polyaromatic hydrocarbons. Diaromatic and polyaromatic hydrocarbons were also observed in the Oak Sawdust (19.7 wt.%) and Spent Grain (9.4 wt.%) HDT liquid middle distillate fraction.

Figure 7. Composition of Naphtha (bp < 175°C), Kerosene (bp = 175-250°C), and middle distillate fractions in the liquid product obtained from the HDT of the HTL crude oils. The compositions were determined through GCxGC/FID by the boiling points of a mixture of linear alkane hydrocarbons (C₆-C₄₄) as reference. Distillation curves in Figure 5.

Despite all HTL crude oils having been produced under identical conditions, the nature of the feedstock significantly changed the composition of the obtained crude oil, which affected the yield and composition of the HDT products, and, consequently, their potential for fuel production. Among the multiple feedstocks, Lignite oil was the only one with no heteroatom compounds found in the HDT liquid by comprehensive GC×GC chromatography (Table 6). Furthermore, Lignite displayed the highest concentration of fuel-range products (62.3 wt.% - Figure 6), with the third highest HDT liquid yield (58.8 wt.%). Hence, Lignite HTL crude oil is a promising feedstock for producing hydrocarbon fuels, particularly when compared with the remaining feedstocks. Nonetheless, the hydrocarbons in the Lignite HDT liquid fuel range contain a significant fraction of aromatic hydrocarbons (Figure 7), which are often less desirable than aliphatic hydrocarbons. Still, a secondary hydrotreatment upgrading or harsher HDT conditions could be used to increase the aliphatic content from Lignite and further increase the fuel yield from this feedstock. Alternatively, blending the fuel fractions with another aliphatic fuel equivalent can also be employed.

Despite its potential, the fossil nature of Lignite makes it a less desirable source from an environmental point of view. However, all renewable feedstocks HDT liquid products displayed a significant concentration of heteroatom-containing compounds and polyaromatics in the kerosene and middle distillates fuel range (Figure 7), which represents the majority of the fuel products. Thus, for these products to replace standard fossil fuels, a secondary hydrotreatment stage and harsher HDT conditions must be employed. Indeed, M.S. Haider et al. showed that, through a secondary hydrotreatment stage, even high N contents in HTL crude, like sewage sludge and Spent Grain, can be removed⁵⁶.

Among the tested renewable feedstocks, Oak Sawdust and Spent Grain displayed the highest concentration of fuel-range products in the HDT liquid, i.e., 55.7 wt.% and 55.6 wt.%, respectively, with the former being equally selective to products in the range of kerosene (24.5 wt.%) and middle distillates (25.4 wt.%), and the latter containing more middle distillates (38.6 wt.%). In addition to fuel

yield distribution, the nature of the products in kerosene and middle distillates range for Oak Sawdust and Spent grain is substantially different. For instance, Oak Sawdust contains no aromatic nitrogenated compounds, which are particularly resistant to hydrotreatment. In opposition, Spent grain yields a significantly higher concentration of aliphatic hydrocarbons, particularly paraffins, which are more suitable for fuel purposes. Indeed, like Lignite, Oak Sawdust is highly selective towards aromatic compounds, including polyaromatic compounds (Figure 7). Finally, despite having a similar fuel-range product concentration in the HDT liquid, Oak Sawdust displayed a significantly smaller liquid yield when compared to Spent Grain, i.e., 41.6 wt.% versus 55.5 wt.%, respectively. Hence, Oak Sawdust has a lower potential for fuel production than Spent Grain.

Finally, from all tested feedstocks, the sewage sludge samples displayed the highest HDT liquid yield (63.8 wt.%) and the lowest concentration of fuel range products (40.6 wt.% - 46.7 wt.%). In addition, the composition of the fuel range products was quite similar to that observed for Brewer Spent Grain, except for the absence of polyaromatic hydrocarbons, as expected from the similarities in the compounds present in the crude oils in both sewage sludge and Spent grain HTL crude oils. Overall, the two sewage sludge feedstocks used in this work showed very similar behavior in terms of conversion and product composition despite their different origin, i.e., municipal sewage treatment plant from Poland (Sewage S. 1) and Germany (Sewage S. 2). Indeed, despite the difference in origin, the overall composition of the HTL crude oil was quite similar, most likely due to the similarities in the organic composition of the parent sewage sludge feedstocks, which indicates that sewage sludges with different origins produce crude oils that can be hydrotreated under similar conditions.

4. Conclusion

Five HTL crude oils from different feedstocks were hydrotreated under identical reaction conditions. The characterization of the crude oils revealed an elemental and molecular composition highly influenced by the structural components of the parent feedstock. For instance, HTL crude oil from Oak Sawdust contained a higher concentration of polyaromatic compounds with molecular weights up to 2,000 g/mol originating from lignin. Instead, the Sewage Sludge and Brewer Spent Grain HTL crude

oils displayed a narrower molecular weight distribution, i.e., up to 1,500 g/mol, with a higher concentration of aliphatic chain in the form of amides, which resulted from fatty acids and proteins present on the feedstocks. Similarly, the proteins in the sewage sludge and spent grain feedstocks are responsible for the significant presence of nitrogenated-aromatic compounds, e.g., indoles and carbazoles, in the HTL crude oils. Lignite crude oil also reflected the nature of the low-rank coal feedstock by displaying the highest sulfur content of all crude oils and a high concentration of aromatic compounds.

The composition of the crude oils significantly impacted their transformation during the hydrotreatment stage. Even if, in all cases, the concentration of heteroatoms reduced considerably, among the tested crude oils, Lignite showed the highest potential for producing hydrocarbons with nearly all heteroatoms, i.e., O and S, being removed during the reaction. In opposition, the recalcitrant nature of some nitrogenated compounds, i.e., carbazoles and indole, existent in the Sewage Sludge and Spent Grain crude oils hindered complete nitrogen removal in these samples. Except for Lignite, trace amounts of O (≤ 1 wt.%) were observed in all liquid products after HDT, a phenomenon explained by the presence of compounds that limit the HDO reactions, e.g., nitrogenated compounds (Spent Grain and Sewage Sludge), or by the higher concentration of O in the parent crude oil (Oak Sawdust).

The nature of the hydrocarbon compounds produced during the hydrotreatment of the crude oils was also impacted by their composition. For instance, the Sewage Sludge and Spent Grain samples displayed higher selectivity towards aliphatic hydrocarbons, particularly paraffins, which are a direct product of the aliphatic compounds, e.g., amides, abundantly present in both these feedstocks. In opposition, Oak Sawdust and Lignite were particularly selective into aromatic hydrocarbon and naphthenes, which are a product of the hydrotreatment of phenol and other aromatic compounds highly abundant in these crude oils. Hence, it is clear that different HTL feedstocks will yield different types of hydrocarbons, which will not have the same potential for fuel production.

Finally, all HDT liquid products would benefit from a sequential treatment stage to increase the liquid yield, decrease the polyaromatic content in the fuel range, and remove the heteroatoms, particularly N and O, in the fuel range. Nonetheless, the conditions and purpose of the secondary treatment stage must be adapted to the composition of the liquid, whose nature is intimately linked to the feedstock used to produce the HTL crude oil.

5. Supporting information. HTL product separation scheme (Figure S1); ^{13}C NMR spectra, SEC-DAD chromatograms, comprehensive GC×GC/TOF-MS and GC×GC/MS of HTL crude oils and HDT liquid products (Figures S2- S4 and S6-S8); GC/FPD⁺ chromatogram of lignite crude oil (Figure S5); SEC-DAD chromatograms of aromatic standards (Figure S9-S12); Composition of HTL feedstocks (Table S1-S5); HTL reaction products yield (Table S6); Catalyst composition (Table S7); ^{13}C and ^{31}P -NMR chemical shifts attribution (Tables S8-S9); Equipment parameters of GC×GC/MS, GC×GC/TOF-MS, and GC×GC/FID (Tables S10-S11); Semi-quantitative XRF analysis of the crude oils and fresh and spent catalysts (Tables S12-S13).

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